

Project CHANGES - Spoke 4

D7 – Guidelines and best practices for technology-aided narratives
for museums and art collections – v1.0

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7	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	UNIFE	Affiliated by “convenzione”
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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we present 1) the approach we have developed for analysing the literature of the last few years (2019-2023), as well as the tool we have applied for analysing the literature of the last decade, according to the methodology proposed at the end of August 2023. Also, we provide an extensive description of one of the “core” case studies of the project, which we have used as a representative scenario to extract and provide the guidelines and best practices for addressing digitisation in museums as a cultural issue.

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1. Introduction

Over the past months, the aim has been to study and develop a tool for analysing the literature of the last decade, according to the methodology proposed at the end of August 2023. In addition, thanks to the preparatory work done in the context of one of our “core” case studies, i.e. that of the “Collezione di geologia “Museo Giovanni Capellini” of the University of Bologna, we have drawn up some guidelines for addressing digitisation in museums as a cultural issue.

2. Verification of the state of the art from a bibliographic point of view using the PRISMA method

As for the first point, that of literature analysis, we have tried to develop a scientific method based on the methodology proposed at the end of the first semester.

A first attempt, done before August 2023, was to produce a selected bibliography using more traditional methods, drawing on a general database (Scopus), using a search string that included the terms “Museum; objects; narrative” in a time span from 2019 to 2023.

However, we were unsatisfied with the results because they did not produce a representative sample, and subjective interpolation was very strong.

We then decided to try to use a tool created for meta-analyses in the medical-scientific field, which is one of the most advanced, i.e. the widely tested PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 method. The system has the advantage of combining qualitative and quantitative assessments and drawing on even mixed databases, such as ours. The field of Cultural Heritage does not have reference databases, but contributions relating to it end up in large international bibliographic indexes (Scopus,

Google Scholar, etc.). The PRISMA 2020 Checklist is extremely articulated: while preserving its structure, we have decided to maintain scientific rigour, condensing specific passages proper to medical-scientific domains. Essential steps: Title, Abstract, Introduction, Methods (Identification of new studies via databases and Screening), Results, Discussion.

The first step of the process consisted of preparing the research strings to use for the research on the database. We have started using the same general terms used in the first research: "Museum", "Digital", and "Narrative".

Then, we proceeded by creating research strings. The result has been the following:

```
((digital) OR (digitalization) OR (mapping) OR (technologies) OR  
(visualisation) OR (virtuality) OR (virtual reality) OR  
(augmented reality) OR (artificial intelligence) OR (digital  
applications) OR (gamification) OR (3D applications) OR (digital  
twin)) AND ((Museum) OR (museums) OR (collection) OR  
(collections) OR (intangible cultural heritage) OR (objects) OR  
(material culture) OR (documents) OR (archive) OR (community) OR  
(history) OR (memory) OR (art) OR (natural science museums) OR  
natural history museums)) AND ((narrative) OR (knowledge  
paradigms) OR (ontology) OR (approaches) OR (perspective) OR  
(rhetoric) OR (construction) OR (de-construction) OR (vision) OR  
(chronology) OR (postmodern) OR (geography) OR (past-oriented)  
OR (present-oriented) OR (national) OR (transnational) OR  
(global) OR (international) OR (imperialism) OR (colonial) OR  
(post-colonial) OR (discipline) OR (inclusion))
```

The terms used were:

- Digital
 - digitalization

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- mapping
- technologies
- visualisation
- virtuality
- virtual reality
- augmented reality
- artificial intelligence
- digital applications
- gamification
- 3D applications
- digital twin
- **Museum**
 - Museums
 - Collection
 - Collections
 - intangible cultural heritage
 - objects
 - material culture
 - documents
 - archive
 - community
 - history
 - memory
 - art
 - natural science museums
 - natural history museums

- Narrative
 - knowledge paradigms
 - ontology
 - approaches
 - perspective
 - rhetoric
 - construction
 - de-construction
 - vision
 - chronology
 - postmodern
 - geography
 - past-oriented
 - present-oriented
 - national
 - transnational
 - global
 - international
 - imperialism
 - colonial
 - post-colonial
 - discipline
 - inclusion

We applied the search on Google Scholar by adding a time range of the years 2014-2024.

This attempt produced a response of over one million items.

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We then tried to change the order of the search by reversing the order and starting not with “museums” but with “digital”. In this second case, the results were reduced to around 20.000, and the digital theme emerged correctly. One aspect, however, was peculiar, namely, the fact that the element of storytelling was, in any case, excluded from the research.

We then tried different research options:

a) ((digital) OR (digitalization) OR (mapping) OR (technologies) OR (visualisation) OR (virtuality) OR (virtual reality) OR (augmented reality) OR (artificial intelligence) OR (digital applications) OR (gamification) OR (3D applications) OR (digital twin)) AND ((Museum) OR (museums) OR (collection) OR (collections) OR (intangible cultural heritage) OR (objects) OR (material culture) OR (documents) OR (archive) OR (community) OR (history) OR (memory) OR (art) OR (natural science museums) OR natural history museums) OR (narrative) OR (knowledge paradigms) OR (ontology) OR (approaches) OR (perspective) OR (rhetoric) OR (construction) OR (de-construction) OR (vision) OR (chronology) OR (postmodern) OR (geography) OR (past-oriented) OR (present-oriented) OR (national) OR (transnational) OR (global) OR (international) OR (imperialism) OR (colonial) OR (post-colonial) OR (discipline) OR (inclusion))

b) ((Museum) OR (museums) OR (collection) OR (collections) OR (intangible cultural heritage) OR (objects) OR (material culture) OR (documents) OR (archive) OR (community) OR (history) OR (memory) OR (art) OR (natural science museums) OR natural history museums) OR (narrative) OR (knowledge paradigms) OR (ontology) OR (approaches) OR (perspective) OR (rhetoric) OR (construction) OR (de-construction) OR

(vision) OR (chronology) OR (postmodern) OR (geography) OR
(past-oriented) OR (present-oriented) OR (national) OR
(transnational) OR (global) OR (international) OR
(imperialism) OR (colonial) OR (post-colonial) OR
(discipline) OR (inclusion)) AND ((digital) OR
(digitalization) OR (mapping) OR (technologies) OR
(visualisation) OR (virtuality) OR (virtual reality) OR
(augmented reality) OR (artificial intelligence) OR
(digital applications) OR (gamification) OR (3D
applications) OR (digital twin))

The results still do not entirely satisfy our purpose, but then again, we realise that applying PRISMA to humanistic research requires complex but interesting thinking to try and produce a new tool. The complexity we have detected is the existence of another field besides digitalisation and museums, i.e., semantics. Indeed, as noted in the domain literature, semantic heterogeneity, which refers to the misinterpretation of data at the schema level, is a primary issue in retrieving cultural heritage information from museum data sources.

The systematic analysis of the abstracts on the selection 'digital' AND 'museum' AND 'narrative' was the most consistent with our objectives.

Although a more stabilised semantic analysis would perhaps be helpful, a reasoned bibliography was nevertheless possible. It suffers from the use of a database, i.e. Google Scholar, which results in a high number of results. In this case, we applied the PRISMA method and specifically analysed the first pages of the results. The bibliography we extracted from this analysis is described in Annex 1.

3. Suggestions from the “Core” Case Studies – Museo Giovanni Capellini

If we take the archive, where present, as an angle of perspective, understood in its broadest meaning (not only written documentation), we could reason not only in terms of sources but as a model. On the one hand, the archive could then serve as a structural model for museums and conservators from different backgrounds who are working in different fields. On the other hand, *museum archives / museums as archives* prove to be essential resources offering insights and information. By applying the historical method of reordering and inventorying also to museum archives, new practices of studying and approaching documentation can be proposed to provide useful tools for conservators and researchers. In this way, the semantic and formal contents of the collections could achieve innovative results.

3.1. “Core” case study under analysis: Collections of the Giovanni Capellini Museum

To initiate a rethinking/renewed narrative of the collections of the “Giovanni Capellini Museum” Geology Collection of the University of Bologna, a reorganisation of the archive kept in the Museum’s own exhibition building, in via Zamboni 63, was also initiated. The aim was to reorder the papers, recondition them and produce an analytical inventory while also reasoning about the possibilities of linking this work to the entire digitalization process.

The first step will be to make the inventory of the Museum Archive- Giovanni Capellini Direction available on the digital platform ParER (Polo archivistico dell’Emilia-Romagna), in x-dams format. This is a system that allows at the same time to link any other inventories made with the same programmes: this is the case of the Giovanni Capellini Special Fund, Fondazione CHANGES - Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society

kept at the Biblioteca Comunale dell'Archiginnasio in Bologna, which consists of 159 envelopes, mostly correspondence from 1851 to 1922. In 2022, a database of this material was created on the basis of the printed inventory, which can be queried from the website of the Archiginnasio Library.

Making a digital inventory will also make it possible to virtually link and make available information on other documentary collections connected to the figure of Giovanni Capellini: first of all, of course, the archive kept at the Accademia Lunigianese di Scienze Giovanni Capellini, in La Spezia.

An archive such as this one also makes it possible to link papers to objects: not only those preserved on site but also, for example, the collection of honours kept at the Library of the Museo del Risorgimento in Bologna (2 archive envelopes - 19 items), which are also described on the ParER digital platform. Digital description and metadata will make it possible to unite these different types of material.

A second phase of work should instead allow us to reason about the possibility of digitising and meta-database any archival series linked to the inventory and made available directly from the Museum's website. This intervention could concern the photographic fund and the fund of geological maps produced by Giovanni Capellini during his activity.

Finally, one could reason for the possibility of constructing, from specific documentation, some digital paths aimed at restoring a renewed narrative of the Capellini Museum's collections and history. The papers preserved in it certainly give us a glimpse of the history of the construction of a collection in line with the evolution of natural sciences during the season that "opened" in the second half of the 19th century in a newly constituted Italian state, but at the same time allows us to reflect on different temporalities and spatiality. As far as the Bolognese Museum's collection is concerned, the interweaving of the various archives can tell a story that originated in the Napoleonic season, when the entire curriculum and disciplines of the "old" study were renewed and continued throughout the "long 19th

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century". The papers, travel diaries, and correspondence then make it possible to visualise a network of relationships that opened to Europe and the world beyond the Atlantic. Temporality and spatiality are what digital narration will make visible and available.

The idea of starting from the case study of the Capellini Museum seemed to us the most appropriate option for drafting guidelines for digitisation applied to cultural heritage for several reasons. First, it presents a very rare case in the 19th century, a paper archive that is integrated in an almost mirror-like manner with collections of objects. Constructed and conceived by Giovanni Capellini in that post-unification period in which the scientific disciplines themselves were being reorganised, the Museum presents itself as a "case" that is certainly peculiar, but capable of providing a "guiding model". Second, however particular and disciplined it may be, it has, both in terms of the figure of Giovanni Capellini and the character of the collections, made it possible to establish an interdisciplinary dialogue applicable as a basis for analysis and reflection.

From the comparison between conservators, archivists, historians, and computer scientists, it was thus possible to attempt to construct paths for elaborating those guidelines reproduced below.

4. Guidelines for addressing digitisation in museums as a cultural issue

A. Contextual analysis of the Museum as a historicised current container

It means studying the museum's location in the physical and diachronic articulation of the city or territory in which it is located. If it is located in the network of heritage 'semiophors', if it is a recognised 'central place' or if, vice versa, its profile is still peripheral with respect to the cultural enhancement and visitor flows.

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B. Analysis of present documentation (catalogues, inventories, papers, objects): state of preservation

A photograph recording the degree of the institution's 'awareness' of its past, digital and otherwise, and what it has become over time. Regulatory or statutory passages are particularly useful for this check-in. But catalogues/inventories in their sedimentation - and thus as objects in themselves, not mere media - from paper to digital are also an effective indicator.

C. Study of demand versus expectations of conservators

It seems impossible to establish any museum activity without the active participation of those who work there. A cultural intervention, even the most sophisticated, cannot fail to impact the improvement of the permanent quality of the offer. Therefore, constructing an activity taking into account the wishes of the curators - even independently of the content of the cultural proposal - is considered an action destined to produce positive legitimising effects.

D. Study of demand versus audience

To whom does this Museum speak? And, above all, recovering the ICOM definition of Museum (Prague 2022), how does it relate to accessibility, inclusion, community, etc.? The issue, always complex, is that of studying demand. Indeed, reducing the question to a mere communication affair is impossible. Striving to find one's interlocutors - bearing in mind that museums are by definition born 'generalists', i.e., aimed at speaking to everyone - means better defining one's project.

E. Study of demand in relation to current transnational or global issues

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How does it fit in? Is there a benchmark to be taken into account? In this case, the literature is abundant, and the case history is very rich. According to the most successful research axes concern colonial/post-colonial issues, gender, cultural inclusion, accessibility.

F. Building on the three previous studies, a negotiating midpoint must be constructed between the actors in the project construction phase. This participative operation decides the feasibility of the project, in addition to the technological and material resources.

- **Identification of the scope of digitisation with respect to needs and constraints.**
Relationship with preservation needs. We now enter the perimeter determined by the reconciliation with the nature of the site and its contents as is. Reconciliation with the physicality of the museum is a delicate but necessary operation. It is not possible to land a digital object in a traditional museum without having logically and materially prepared its context.
- **Construction of the narrative** and thus the use of digitisation at several levels (cataloguing, enjoyment of exhibited or remote objects, 3D, immersion, digital twin). In general, the approach identified aims to consider digitisation as an integrated process, not only of enhancement of existing objects but of true creation of originally digital objects.
- Ours is the canvas of a story that fits into a sphere not all subject to transformation. How does it coexist with the rest? That museums are self-referential monads (natively static) and objects instead nomadic, not only because they are physically mobile, but because they are culturally subject to narrative enrichment, is perhaps a truism. Perceiving and reflecting on the effects of inserting such elements of fluidity into a pre-existing structure with its own (strong or weak) tradition is an unavoidable step for curators and researchers.

- On the one hand, **evaluation of the technological impact is a transitional element** and, on the other hand, it helps read the evolution of demand. Digitisation, therefore, does not translate into a new updated static concept but must be selective and live with change. It must be used as a permanent laboratory. This is perhaps the most complex step: inserting a digital narrative capable of evolving and adapting to the transformations of the context. An example: from the digitisation used in an exhibition to the digitisation of a temporary exhibition, or from the evocation of an introductory reading context in a traditional key to an immersive proposal, acting on emotional rather than rational attraction.

G. A final (self-critical) element is the evaluation of rhetoric related to the progressivism of technology

Beyond the initial communication, necessarily characterised by the accentuation of the elements of innovation and astonishment, it is useful to reflect, after some time, on the actual impact of the project on the museum/landscape/territory reality and its "legacy", in terms of increase of the permanent museum offer, of legitimisation, of accreditation, of interception of the demand imagined at the origin of the route. This is a rationalisation operation, which is all the more necessary as the rhetorical framework generally guides the enhancement.

Annex 1: bibliography produced with the “PRISMA Method”

Terms used: **Digital AND Museum AND Narrative**

Time window: 2014-2024

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Total results: 17.200 results

Primary results (first 8 pages):

- Bucchiarone, A. (2022). Gamification and virtual reality for digital twin learning and training: architecture and challenges. *Virtual Reality & Intelligent Hardware*, 4(6), 471-486.
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